

THE ROLE OF PERCEPTIVE-REFLECTIVE AND AUTOPSYCHOLOGICAL COMPETENCE IN THE PROFESSIONAL FORMATION OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract: This article explores the psychological and acmeological characteristics of the professional training process of future teachers. The study analyzes the perceptive-reflexive abilities, emotional reactions, and communication culture of the future specialist's personality. Furthermore, based on scientific sources, the mechanisms of forming a professional "Self-image" through the level of self-esteem, internal motivation, and autopsychological competence of the future teacher are extensively covered.

Keywords: *future teacher, perceptive-reflexive abilities, autopsychological competence, intrinsic motivation, pedagogical reflection, acmeology, self-assessment.*

In the modern stage of pedagogical science, it is impossible to envision the formation of a future teacher without the acmeological approach. Acmeology studies the phenomenology, patterns, and mechanisms of human development at the stage of maturity, especially during the period when one reaches their highest level ("Acme") [1:73]. Conditions that enhance the sense of competence for a future teacher should also increase their intrinsic motivation. According to E. Deci, the pursuit of competence and mastery can be considered the most crucial educational and professional need. The more effectively an activity allows the future teacher to feel competent, the higher their intrinsic motivation will be.

Research by R. Vallerand and G. Reid demonstrated that information about success increases the sense of competence, while failures decrease it [2:116]. For a future teacher, activities of moderate difficulty are optimal, as the inevitable negative feedback in such situations helps the student recognize their weaknesses and improve their skills.

N.V. Kuzmina distinguishes three types of perceptual-reflexive abilities that reflect the inner aspect of the relationship between the future teacher and students [3:119]:

1. Object perception: The future teacher's sensitivity to how students reflect the object of real reality. This is related to empathy and requires quick and deep insight into the student's psychology.

2. Sense of measure or tact: The ability to identify changes (positive or negative) occurring in the student's personality and activities under various pedagogical influences.

3. Sense of involvement: The future teacher's sensitivity to the achievements and shortcomings of their own activity and personality, that is, understanding how they are perceived by students.

Pedagogical reflection is a professionally important quality of the future teacher's personality, which is characterized as a type of intellectual activity [4:301]. The emotional sphere of psychological competence is manifested in the reactions of the future teacher. These can be evaluative, defensive, or regulatory in content; aggressive, conciliatory, or rationalizing in the nature of activity [5:221].

S.V. Ryzhova views the communicative component as the culture of the future teacher aimed at establishing interpersonal relationships [6:20]. A.K. Markova identifies a number of communicative tasks for the future teacher: mutual understanding, the ability to see oneself

through the eyes of a communication partner, mobilization of resources, and self-presentation in accordance with pedagogical goals [7:192].

Differential-psychological competence represents the future teacher's knowledge of individual characteristics, abilities, and strengths of each student's character. In the preparation of future teachers, guiding students' self-education performs important functions: pedagogical promotion, diagnostics, and organization of the process [8:22]. For this, the future specialist must develop analytical-perceptual, diagnostic, and prognostic skills [9:144].

The essence of autopsychological competence consists of the future teacher's awareness of the strengths and weaknesses of their personality and activities, as well as measures to improve the quality of their work. This depends on the level of social intelligence and involves the ability to predict relationships.

The future teacher's attitude towards themselves is determined by three aspects:

1. Comparison of the "I-real" and "I-ideal" images. The self-esteem formula is the ratio of success to claims (pretensions): $\text{Self-esteem} = \text{Success} / \text{Claims}$.

2. Internal acceptance of social reactions. A person tends to evaluate themselves based on the assessment given to them by others (C. Cooley's "Looking-glass Self" concept).

3. Identification. An individual derives satisfaction from performing their chosen work well [10:129].

Psychological studies show that inadequate and unstable professional self-assessment has an inverse correlation with success. An inadequately high self-evaluation leads to a decrease in the level of activity.

Analysis of the person-centered educational paradigm demonstrates that the competence of a future teacher is not merely a sum of knowledge, but an integration of their personal and professional qualities. The intrinsic connection between socio-psychological, differential, and autopsychological competencies is a necessary condition for the development of the future specialist as a subject of labor. Investigating the psychological and pedagogical competence of a future teacher as a self-expressive personality remains a promising scientific problem.

In summary, it should be emphasized that the professional formation of a future teacher results not only from external skills but also from profound psychological and autopsychological transformations. The development of perceptual-reflective abilities enables the future teacher to sense the student's world and select appropriate tactics in pedagogical communication. The stability of self-esteem and the formation of autopsychological competence are the primary mechanisms guiding the future specialist towards the level of professional "Acme" (peak), which serve to enhance stress resistance and systematically improve the professional self-image. Thus, the targeted development of the emotional-volitional and reflective sphere of the future teacher's personality serves as a fundamental foundation for their future effective self-realization and pedagogical creativity.

Adabiyotlar, References, Литературы:

1. Бодалев А.А. О предмете акмеологии // Психологический журнал. 1993.- Т. 14; №5.- С. 73-79.
2. Чирков В.И. Самодетерминация и внутренняя мотивация поведения человека // Вопросы психологии. - 1996.- № 3.- С. 116-132.

3. Кузьмина Н.В. Профессионализм личности преподавателя и мастера производственного обучения. - М.: Высш. шк., 1990 -119 с.
4. Яковлева Л.В. Педагогическая форма рефлексии как компонент профессиональной культуры учителя // Профессионально-педагогическая культура: история, теория, технология: Мат. Всерос. научн-практич. Конф. 9-11 октября - Белгород: Изд-во Белгородского гос. ун-та, 1996.
5. Попова Е.В. Профессионально-педагогическая компетентность как условие повышения педагогической культуры: Дис. ...канд.пед.наук - Ростов-на-Дону, 1996 - 221 с.
6. Рыжова С.В. Развитие творческой самостоятельности учителя на курсах повышения квалификации в ННУ: Автореф. дис. ...канд.пед.наук.- Н.Новгород, 1992.-20 с.
7. Маркова А.К. Психология труда учителя: Кн. для учителя - М.: Просвещение. 1993.-192 с.
8. Дудина И.И. профессионально-педагогический самовоспитание студентов: Автореф. дис. ...канд.пед. наук -Рязань, 1975. - 22 с.
9. Счастливленко А.Г. Прогнозирование в личностно-ориентированном обучении // Личностно ориентированное обучение в воспитание: Тез. доклада межвуз. научн. конф. 26-27 октября 1994 - Волгоград: Перемена, 1994. Проф. деятельность молодого учителя: Социально-педагогический аспект. /Под ред. С.Г. Вершиловского, Л.И. Лесохиной. - М.: Педагогика, 1982. 144 с.
10. Полякова Т.С. Анализ затруднений в педагогической деятельности начинающих учителей. / Предисл. действ, чл. АПН СССР Ю.К. Бабанского. - М.: Педагогика, 1983. - 129 с.